
Effect of Soil Type on the Growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* (A. Chev.)

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Abstract

Terminalia ivorensis is a tree species found in lowland rainforest zone in Nigeria but is predominantly a tree of seasonal forest zones. Nursery experiment was carried out to investigate the effect of soil type on the growth of *Terminalia ivorensis*. Different soil types were collected namely: sandy, clay and loamy soils. Seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* were broadcasted on a germination bed at the college nursery and later, were transplanted into polythene pots containing the different soil types. The parameters assessed include total height, stem diameter and leaf production. *Terminalia ivorensis* seeds grown on loamy soil gave the best result in both total height and stem diameter (10.22 cm and 0.20 cm respectively) while *Terminalia ivorensis* seeds raised on sandy soil gave the best result for leaf count (8.17). Seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* performed better on sandy soil, best on loamy soil and less on clay soil. Seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* performed well in total height on loamy soil (9.48 cm), in stem diameter on sandy soil (0.17 cm) and in number of leaves both in sandy and clay soil (7.25). The seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* performed well in total height and stem diameter on loamy soil (9.97 cm and 0.19 cm respectively) and had the same value for number of leaves in the three soil samples (7.08). Based on the findings of this work, it is hereby recommended that *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings should be raised using loamy soil.

Keywords: *Terminalia ivorensis*, Soil, Growth, Seeds, Species

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Introduction

Terminalia ivorensis is a tree species found in lowland rainforest zone in Nigeria but is predominantly a tree of seasonal forest zones. The species is one of the most important of some 200 species belonging to the genus *Terminalia*. Germination is the resumption of active embryo growth after a dormant period. The seed must be viable (the embryo must be alive and capable of germination). Low seed germination (vigor) is a function of the age and storage conditions of the planted seed as well as the health and maturity of the plant from which the seed was harvested. Internal conditions of the seed must be favorable for germination, that is, any physical, chemical, or physiological barriers to germination must have disappeared or must have been removed. The seed must be subjected to appropriate environmental conditions, including water (moisture), proper temperature, oxygen, and for some species, light. Forest-tree seeds have different germination rates and optimal temperatures (Ball, 2011).

In the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, many foresters and amateur geologist became interested in the reason for the distribution of different types of soil. They came to the general conclusion that there was a direct and fairly simple relationship between the character of the soil and the nature of the underlying soil parent material. They found chalky soils on chalk; sandy soils on sandstone, clayey soils on shale and organic soils on peat and so, they devised soil classifications which were based on the nature of the rock beneath it (Yeates and Darrah, 1991).

Soils vary enormously in their physical and chemical properties owing to the nature of the parental material. Differences in the litho logical characteristics of the parent rock are of salient importance for two main reasons. Firstly, rocks differ enormously in the amount of soluble plant nutrient that they liberate on weathering. Secondly, the residue of weathering can vary between almost 100% clay and almost 100% quartz although; most rocks yield a residue, which contains a certain amount of both individual clay particles are exceedingly small, all having a diameter of less than 0.002mm. Quartz grains on the other hand are nearly all much larger in size, those with a diameter between 0.002mm and 0.02mm being referred to as silt and those with above 0.02mm as sand. It is clear that the larger the percentage of clay particles in weathered material, the slower will be the rate at which water will percolate through it. On the other hand, very sandy materials will allow water to flow through them almost unimpeded. Soil textures are classified as sandy, silt, clayey and loamy, according to the proportions of the different types of

particle present. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effect of soil type on the growth of *terminalia ivorensis*.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out in Nursery C of the Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. The College is situated at Jericho Hill, Ibadan North West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The area lies between Latitude 7°26'N and Longitude 3°54'E. The annual rainfall ranges from 1400mm - 1500mm and average relative humidity of about 65%, the average temperature is 31.8°C.

Sowing of Seeds and Parameter Assessment

The seeds were broadcasted on a germination bed at the Federal College of Forestry nursery and after two weeks of germination, the seedlings were transplanted into polythene pots containing the different soil types. The following parameters were assessed namely; plant height, leaf production, stem diameter. Readings of the growth performance was taken once in a week.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using ANOVA. The mean was separated using least significant difference.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the analysis of variance for the total height. The results show that there is significant variation among the treatments and also among the soil types while there are no significant variation in the interaction between the treatment and the soil type. Loam soil shows the highest mean total height to be 5cm, followed by sandy soil which had the mean of 4cm. The lowest mean stem diameter was observed in clay soil which had 2.5cm.

Table 1: Analysis of variance for total height

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	VR	Fpr.
Treatments	8	116.552	14.569	10.59	<.001*
Soil type	7	721.749	103.107	74.96	<.001*
Treatments soil type	56	67.308	1.202	0.87	0.714NS
Residual	144	198.080	1.376		
Total	215	1103.690			

Where * = Significant at 5% level of significance, NS = not significant at 5% level of significance, DMRT = 0.67, Standard Error (S.E) = 1.17

Loam soil shows the highest mean stem diameter to be 0.20cm, followed by sandy soil which had the mean of 0.19cm. The lowest mean stem diameter was observed in clay soil which had 0.13cm. This could be due to the fact that the soil used as loamy soil had the highest value of Nitrogen (0.472) which is considered as one of the most important nutrient for plant development. Nitrogen is important for proper stem growth; this includes both lateral and diameter growth as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance for stem diameter

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	VR	Fpr.
Treatments	8	0.1142417	0.0142802	15.34	<.001*
Soil type	7	0.0851981	0.0121712	13.07	<.001*
Treatments soil type	56	0.0018769	0.0000335	0.04	1.000NS
Residual	144	0.1340667	0.0009310		
Total	215	0.3353833			

DMRT = 0.02, S.E = 0.03

Table 2 shows the analysis of variance for stem diameter, there are significance different among the treatment and also among the soil type, however there are no significant different in the interaction. Table 3 shows that loamy soil had the highest mean leaf number of 8.17, followed by sandy soil with 7.42, while the lowest mean leaf count was observed in clay soil which had 6.75. Sandy soils are well aerated soils which have no capacity of holding water. The roots have more space to extend their tendrils in order to absorb water and nutrient (Bergsma, 1992). Table 3 shows the analysis of variance for leaf production, again there are significant difference among the treatment and soil type while there is no significant difference in their interaction.

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Table 3: Analysis of Variance for Leaf production

Source of variation	DF	SS	MS	VR	F p.r
Treatments	8	29.333	3.667	3.38	0.001*
Soil type	7	1519.481	217.069	200.37	<.001*
Treatments soil type	56	34.519	0.616	0.57	0.991NS
Residual	144	156.000	1.083		
Total	215	1739.333			

DMRT = 0.60, S.E = 1.04

Conclusion

In summary, *Terminalia ivorensis* seeds grown on loamy soil have given the best result in both stem height and stem diameter (10.22cm and 0.20cm respectively) while seeds raised on sandy soil gave the best result for leaf count (8.17). The overall analysis of variance shows that there is significant difference among the treatments and soil types for all the parameters measured. Based on the findings of this work, it is hereby recommended that seedlings should be raised using loamy soil.

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